

PROBLEMS OF USING MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN GENERAL SCHOOLS

A.A. TOLAMETOV

acting professor of the "Pedagogy and Psychology" department, Center for scientific-methodical provision, retraining and professional development of specialists in physical education and sports.

T.A. MAKHAROV

Acting associate professor of the Algorithms and Programming Technologies Department of the Faculty of Applied Mathematics and Intellectual Technologies of NUUz.

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ABSTRACT

Current problems of using modern information and communication technologies from the point of view of pedagogues of physical education in general educational institutions are highlighted.

Relevance. On the basis of the Law "On Education" and the "National Personnel Training Program", strengthening the material-technical and informational base of educational institutions, providing the educational process with advanced pedagogical and information-communication technologies. The work being carried out in this regard is one of the important factors in improving the social development of our country with the training of qualified personnel.

In the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 "On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-5924, broad sections of the population, including general education schools. In order to popularize physical education among pupils, students of professional and higher educational institutions, and to identify talented ones among them, the "General education school sports" festival, the "Physical fitness-advanced institution" examination-competition will be staged (district/city, region, republic) and introduction of the nomination of the best general education school, professional and higher educational institution with improved level of physical training" - emphasized [2].

Also, in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2020 "On measures for the wide implementation of the digital economy and electronic government" No. PQ-4699, one of the main tasks of the further development of the digital economy and electronic government is, the tasks of wide implementation of digital technologies at all stages of the educational system, raising the level of digital knowledge necessary for the modern economy, and improving the educational infrastructure are set. Also, as part of the implementation of the "Five Initiatives" project, it is planned to open digital knowledge training centers in all regions of the republic by 2022 [1].

The development of information and communication technologies in the field of physical education and sports has become a modern demand. The issue of determining the effectiveness of educational processes and improving the activities of physical education teachers of general education institutions based on their knowledge and skills in the use of modern computer technologies and devices, the issue of studying the current situations, needs and interests remains urgent.

The purpose of the work is to clarify the problems in the field of information and communication technologies for physical education teachers of general educational institutions and to analyze the practical importance of this issue.

Research methods - to study and analyze the actual problems of using modern information technologies with physical education teachers working in general education schools in our republic by conducting a questionnaire-survey.

Based on the purpose of our research, we, among physical education teachers working in general education schools in our republic, used cloud technology (Google) questionnaire was conducted online. 672 pedagogues working in the field of physical education in secondary schools took part in this survey. 69.5% of them were men and 30.5% were women. 3.4% of the research participants were aged 18 to 20, 19.9% were aged 20 to 25, 43.9% were aged 26 to 35, and 22.5% were aged 36 to 45. , over 46 years old - 10.3%. According to indicators of completion of educational stages of higher education: 22.9% of masters and 77.1% of bachelors.

87.5% of the respondents said that they use information and communication technologies in their professional activities, 11.9% do not use them, and 0.6% think that it is unnecessary. Such a difference in results is related to the diversity of the specialists' education, qualifications, work experience, and their approach to their professional activity using different methods, as well as the opportunities created for information and communication technologies in the operating educational institutions.

"Does the organization where you work have enough opportunities for information and communication technologies?" 71.4% answered positively, 17.5% negatively and 11.1% could not answer the question.

At present, serious changes in the field of modern information and communication technologies are associated with rapid development. As a result, physical education teachers of general education schools applied the possibilities of information and communication technologies to the educational process, which led to its improvement [3].

The role of modern information and communication technologies in the control and analysis of the level of physical fitness of students in general education schools is incomparable, and now most pedagogues and teachers are using these opportunities widely. This can be seen in the results of the survey.

Umumta'lim maktablarida jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilarining AKTdan foydalanish holati

Figure 1. Status of ICT use

It was found that 84.2% of teachers use a mobile phone, 38.2% use a computer, and 6% use a tablet, while 1.7% of the participants stated that they do not use the possibilities of modern technologies.

The creation of information resources necessary for the use of modern information technologies: mobile phones, computers, tablets in the educational processes of physical education in general education schools has become a requirement of today. This led to the creation of conditions for the use of new forms and methods of education, in addition to traditional teaching methods, a new form of education - the possibilities of information and communication technologies.

As a result of the rapid popularization of modern means of mass communication, they are gaining a great position on the stage of the world media space. This is explained by the respondents' "Which social networks do you mainly use?" - can be seen from his answers to the question:

Figure 2. Status of using social networks

"From what Internet sources do you get news for your professional activities?" The respondents answered the question as follows:

from Ziyonet educational portal - 20.2%;

from YouTube online platform - 50.7%;

from Telegram messenger - 52.3%;

From Instagram - 15.5%;

from Facebook - 13.6%;

From various internet pages - 41.6%.

It follows that increasing the number of national social networks or sites that can compete with such social networks in our republic should be one of the goals of today's web developers.

It is designed to control and analyze the state of physical fitness of students in the package of modern computer applications. With the help of such practical programs, it is possible to choose the most optimal program for the teaching process and create a lesson plan by monitoring and analyzing the physical condition of students. In particular, in the questionnaire "Do you analyze the results of measurements during training using computer programs?" 49.6% of respondents answered positively, 3% of respondents said that they consider it unnecessary, and 47.4% of respondents said that they do not use it.

As a result of using the capabilities of modern computer programs, teachers of physical education will have the opportunity to receive information about the physical development of students and study in detail based on the received information. Thanks to these technologies, it is possible to increase the efficiency of physical education in a short time.

"Do you analyze using multimedia software tools in physical education?" - 67.6% of respondents answered that they use it, 4.1% of respondents said that it is unnecessary, and 28.3% said that they do not use it.

Among the respondents, 93.5% answered the question "Is it possible to develop personal interest, increase interest in health, strengthen abilities and further develop them through the use of multimedia software tools in physical education and sports" - 93.5% - yes, 3.2% and 3.3% answered that it was not useful.

Among those who took part in the survey, "Do you think that textbooks, training manuals and training manuals on the use of information technologies in physical education are sufficient?" - 27.8% answered that it was enough, 72.2% answered that it was not enough.

It is also possible to collect, process, analyze and determine the physical fitness of students with the help of computer technologies.

94.2% of the respondents noted that it is effective to use the capabilities of modern computer programs to improve and monitor the effectiveness of physical education classes.

26% of the respondents said that they monitor the physical condition and health of the contingents of employees with the help of a computer, 66% do not, and 8.1% of the respondents said that they do not know about the existence of such resources.

Electronic resources related to physical education and sports are mainly used by 71.7% of respondents from the state domains of Uzbekistan, 36% from the state domains of Russia, 8.2% from the domains of England and Germany, 22.6% from the domains of other countries, and those who do not know that such resources exist. respondents - 6%. a

49.1% of the respondents said that the electronic resources of textbooks, training manuals, educational methodical recommendations on the websites of Uzbekistan are sufficient, 30.9% are insufficient, and 19.3% of the respondents recognize that they have difficulty answering, emphasized.

In conclusion, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the training system for physical education teachers working in a general education school is effective in managing the educational process, in the systematic objective assessment of their physical and sports performance, in the provision of information, analytical review. It can be noted that the development of the most optimal ways of operation, storage and practical application is of particular importance. Effective use of information and communication technologies in physical education in secondary schools is important, regardless of the methods of use.

References:

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